

Thoughts on the Origin of Life Resulting from General Relativity

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ABSTRACT

From where did life originate? God? Evolution? Panspermia? If the tendency of humans and scientists to regard undiscovered science as pseudoscience can be overcome, Einstein gave another alternative to consider when he introduced General Relativity. Time isn't linear – progressing in a straight line from past to present to future. That assumption ignores Relativity which states that space AND TIME are curved. Where did life and the genetic code come from? Can the answer build AI?

The first question can be answered by the section of this article titled **SETI, Evolution, and Time** which says life and the genetic code came from humans acquiring knowledge of these things over the centuries, then applying that knowledge – via terraforming, accumulation of raw materials like amino acids and nucleic acids, genetic engineering - to a time in the past when life didn't exist. From that origin, life evolved through innumerable mutations and adaptations, with humans once again acquiring knowledge of it in cyclic (nonlinear) time.

The second question is answered by saying artificial intelligence (AI) as the product of life is only half of the equation. The other half refers to Relativity's curved space-time and violation of the notion that time always travels from past to future. We have always lived in an artificially intelligent, non-probabilistic universe where everything in time and space is connected into one thing by quantum entanglement – making the brain and genes products of binary-digit activity or artificial intelligence (life is not merely dependent on biology's "lock and key" mechanisms but also possesses AI).

KEYWORDS

Nonlinear time; Electrical engineering at Yale University; Artificial Intelligence; Quantum determinacy; Cosmology; Biological evolution

ARTICLE

NONLINEAR TIME AND ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING

Deep Learning, progress in Artificial Intelligence, and related subjects are all truly fascinating topics. According to this essay, they're all parts of an overarching topic viz. that the entire universe, including space-time and matter, is composed of Artificial Intelligence. Universal AI is a natural consequence of the cosmos being composed of BITS (Binary digITS). Another result is that quantum probability is merely superficial, emulating Chaos theory which possesses a hidden order within apparent disorder. The article finishes with an example of order within disorder –

INFORMATION THEORY CONQUERS A RED GIANT (preserving Earth by keeping the Sun near today's level of activity forever).

The next section suggests gravitational-electromagnetic unity - an unfulfilled dream of Albert Einstein's - can be achieved via the Mobius strip and figure-8 Klein bottle. These topological figures result from application of the binary digits (1's and 0's) which give the universe Artificial Intelligence. The next part of this section speaks of interstellar and intergalactic travel (with possible time travel into the past and the future) resulting from an electrical-engineering experiment, and from wormholes which provide shortcuts through space and time (and are thus speaking of nonlinear time which bypasses normal routes through time). If time was linear, **BITS AND TOPOLOGY** would logically precede **NONLINEAR TIME AND ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING**. But since it appears to be nonlinear, the reader needs to encounter **NONLINEAR TIME AND ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING** before **BITS AND TOPOLOGY**.

Unifying gravitation and electromagnetism has this consequence: the electrical-engineering experiment (1) at America's Yale University, together with the ideas of Albert Einstein, tells us how we could travel to other stars and galaxies. An electrical engineering team at Yale demonstrated that, on nanoscales, light can attract and repel itself like electric charges or magnets.

This is the Optical Bonding Force. For 30 years until his death in 1955, Einstein worked on his Unified Field Theory with the aim of uniting electromagnetism (light is one form of this) and gravitation. Achievement of

this means the quantum components (gravitons) of gravity/spacetime-warps between spaceships and stars could mimic the Optical Force and be attracted together, thereby eliminating distance (this, possibly acting in partnership with repulsion, could produce a wormhole, or shortcut between folds in space and time). If the gravitons are superposed and entangled, distances between both points in space and points in time are totally eliminated.

BITS AND TOPOLOGY

- a) In 1990, John Wheeler (1911-2008) suggested that information is fundamental to the physics of the universe. According to this "it from bit" doctrine, all things physical are information-theoretic in origin. (2)
- b) Erik Verlinde says gravity is not a fundamental force of nature, but an emergent phenomenon. In the same way that temperature arises from the movement of microscopic particles, gravity emerges from the changes of fundamental bits of information, stored in the very structure of spacetime. (3)
- c) Cosmologist Max Tegmark hypothesizes that mathematical formulas create reality (4)
- d) "Pioneered by Rafael Sorkin, the theory (causal sets) postulates that the building blocks of space-time are simple mathematical points that are connected by links, with each link pointing from past to future." (5)

Electronics' binary digits can be used to draw a two-dimensional computer image of a Mobius strip. Two united Mobius strips create a three-dimensional figure-8 Klein bottle*, (6) that acts as a building block of space, time, forces' bosons and matter's fermions. This creates a supersymmetry (linkage) between fermions and bosons. A recent paper (7) says that in a holographic universe, all of the information in the universe is contained in two-dimensional packages trillions of times smaller than an atom. Therefore, trillions of Mobius strips could form a photon and trillions of more complex figure-8 Klein bottles could form a more complex graviton (suggesting union of electromagnetism and gravitation).

*** Since the Klein is 2-dimensional, the statement about a couple of two-dimensional Mobius strips uniting to form a three-dimensional figure-8 Klein bottle needs further explanation** - A Klein Bottle is a 2-dimensional manifold (collection of points) whose inside is its outside. It can only exist in 4-dimensions! A Klein Bottle cannot be embedded in 3 dimensions, but you can immerse it in 3-D. A photograph of a stapler is a 2-dimensional immersion of a 3-dimensional stapler. (An immersion may have self-intersections, embeddings have no self-intersections.) Since the figure-8 Klein bottle referred to in this article can only exist in 4 dimensions, it can be termed a structure of 3 space dimensions which includes the 4th (time) dimension

described by Wick rotation. The bottle's immersion in 3 dimensions means its self-intersection allows it to possess only one surface - its inside is its outside (other 3-D objects like wine bottles, for example, have both an inside and an outside).

Figure 1 – the Möbius Strip, which is two-dimensional and only has one surface (source: http://www.clker.com/cliparts/3/7/a/9/1220546534781713951lummie_Mobius_Strip.svg.hi.png) The Möbius strip is a closed surface with no distinction between inside and outside. Thanks to quantum mechanics' entanglement applying on macroscopic scales,* this doesn't refer only to the surface itself. This results in the space-time of our universe existing everywhere and everywhen. The inside and outside of the universe's energy and mass are continuous when it's composed of Möbius strips and figure-8 Klein bottles acting macroscopically - there cannot be other universes outside our infinite and eternal universe, and there's no universe with different laws of physics (such a state of supposed multiple universes is called the multiverse).

* "Physicists now believe that entanglement between particles exists everywhere, all the time, and have recently found shocking evidence that it affects the wider, 'macroscopic' world that we inhabit." (8) Though the effect is measured for distances in space, the inseparability of space and time means that moments of time can become entangled too. (9)

The physicist and science historian Abraham Pais wrote that "In 1924 the scientist Wolfgang Pauli was the first to propose a doubling of electron states due to a two-valued non-classical "hidden rotation". (10) Extending the ideas of "doubling", "two-valued" and "hidden rotation" from the quantum spin Pauli had in mind to the Möbius strip being a basic, fundamental unit of reality; it can be seen that Pauli's proposal has an analogy to this article. The doubled Möbius strips (doubled to form a figure-8 Klein bottle) could be produced by the two-valued binary-digit system used in electronics. The bottles possess a

hidden rotation, now identified as adaptive Wick rotation, which gives a fourth dimension to space-time.

Figure 2 - MOBIUS DOUBLET (FIGURE-8 KLEIN BOTTLE) (source: <https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/7/73/KleinBottleFigure8-01.png>) Note that the positive curvature fits together with the negative curvature to produce the outline of a doughnut which is technically flat (see the reference to Vanessa Janek (11)). When many doublets are placed together, binary digits can fill in any gaps or voids in the same way that computers can morph a picture on a screen and extrapolate a small patch of blue sky to make a sky that's blue from horizon to horizon. Morphing by bits can also delete a single doublet's central "hole". But the doublet doesn't become multiply connected like the doughnut. Merely the doughnut's outline is adopted – the doublet retains the property of being simply connected, a property necessary for space-time's infinity. (Informally, if an object in space consists of one piece - the constituent two Mobius strips now have the outline of one doughnut - and no longer has any "holes" that pass all the way through it, it is called simply-connected. A flat universe that is also simply connected implies an infinite universe. (12)

WICK ROTATION, CAUSALITY, AND UNITING TIME

Figure 3 – WICK ROTATION: “The complex plane reveals i ’s special relationship with cycles via the circle of i , also known as Wick rotation. Whenever a point on the complex plane is multiplied by i , it moves a quarter rotation around the origin or center of the plane.” [Figure and quote from (13)] Wick Rotation’s applications aren’t restricted to soon-to-be-mentioned time dilation, dark matter and dark energy. Electromagnetic waves* are described by science as transverse, as are water waves. If a stone is dropped into a pool of calm water, many circular waves soon cover the surface of the water, and the water appears to be moving outwards from where the stone was dropped in. Actually, the particles of water simply rise then fall – it’s the wave motion that moves outward. Similarly, there is little movement of photons - they simply rise and fall like corks bobbing up and down in the ocean’s waves. Energy is transferred from photons in one place to photons in the next place by travelling space-time disturbances, and this wave motion is what is referred to as an electromagnetic wave. In Figure 3, photons rise from the positive branch of the x-axis (to the right of the origin or centre) to the positive y-axis (extending above the origin). Then the photons fall to the negative x-axis, and continue falling to the negative y-axis. Then they rise to the positive x and resume their rotation. The conclusions are (1) the energy of electromagnetic and gravitational waves composing space-time and mass rotate in a circle, giving rise to other large-scale dimensions where so-called dark energy doesn’t produce universal expansion but, following $E=mc^2$, does produce what science calls dark matter, and (2) if there is little movement of photons (and gravitons), the universe could not be expanding (or contracting) but its space and time is static. The Big Bang has impressive points ... leading to the idea that it’s a necessary stepping-stone. For example, the Big Bang’s supposed origin from quantum fluctuations is reminiscent of bits switching between 1 and 0.

* "When we solve (19th-century Scottish physicist James Clerk) Maxwell's equations for light, we find not one but two solutions: a 'retarded' wave, which represents the standard motion of light from one point to another; but also an 'advanced' wave, where the light beam goes backward in time. (^ note by author of "Riemann Hypothesis ...") Engineers have simply dismissed the advanced wave as a mathematical curiosity since the retarded waves so accurately predicted the behavior of radio, microwaves, TV, radar, and X-rays. But for physicists, the advanced wave has been a nagging problem for the past century." (14) Einstein's equations say gravitational fields carry enough information about electromagnetism to allow Maxwell's equations to be restated in terms of these gravitational fields. This was discovered by the mathematical physicist George Yuri Rainich. (15) Therefore, gravitational waves also have advanced components going back in time. 1's and 0's composing electromagnetic and gravitational waves would compose both "advanced" waves going back in time and "retarded" waves going forward in time. The retarded components with +x motion in time can obviously cancel the advanced components with -x motion in time, producing entanglement. 17th century scientist Isaac Newton's idea of gravity acting instantly across the universe could be explained by gravity's ability to travel back in time, and thereby reach a point billions of light years away not in billions of years, but in negative billions-of-years. That is; the negative/advanced component of a gravitational wave would already be at its destination as soon as it left its source**, and its journey is apparently instant.

** Arriving at its destination billions of years before it left its source is an absurd impossibility if we cling to the traditional view of time flowing in one direction from cause to effect. But it's plausible if we accept the Block Universe theory which developed from Special Relativity's non-simultaneity of events for different observers. In the Block Universe, all time coexists (the entire past, the present, and every point in the future all exist at once) - in the same way that every period of time in a movie exists simultaneously on a store-bought DVD. Time can be visualized as a Cosmic DVD where our brains and consciousnesses take the place of the DVD player's laser. Everything in the Cosmic DVD's time exists at once*** but we're only aware of an extremely limited number of events at any instant (these make up our present). Gravitational waves arriving billions of years prior to emission can be compared to playing part of the Cosmic DVD in reverse. Waves travel from a later frame of the cosmic movie to an earlier frame.

*** All mass is composed of gravitational and electromagnetic waves. Both types of waves possess retarded and advanced components which entangle all masses. Wick rotation (time) is built into the Mobius strips and figure-8 Klein bottles composing electromagnetism's photons and gravitation's gravitons. Therefore, all time (the entire past and present and future) is united

into one thing just as all space and all mass are united into one thing. This article says space and mass are united and physics already accepts that space and time are united. If space, mass (including the bosons of the weak and strong nuclear forces), time, electromagnetism, and gravitation are all aspects of the same thing; that suggests the theory of quantum gravity truly exists. Mathematical equations would be just another aspect of the one thing - a tool - which people deem necessary to prove quantum gravity.

DIGITAL BRAIN, DIGITAL UNIVERSE

If the brain and the universe are ultimately composed of binary digits, we'll someday be able to do the same things with the brain and universe that we now do with computers. We'll be able to record and share any information in any part of the brain. We'll be able to transfer (download) the brain's contents into another body or an android - infinite times if necessary - and thus say hello to immortality. When quantum mechanics and General Relativity are united into quantum gravity or the Theory of Everything, we'll have access to everything in space and time. Then we can upload the products of the brain's frontal cortex anywhere to influence anything. We can either add to it (mimicking a computer's copy/paste function), remove (delete) part of it, or change the way it proceeds (reprogram it).

I don't think it'll be possible to change history or to reprogram something to behave differently from the way future history has recorded. This is because I believe time can be visualized as a Cosmic DVD where our brains and consciousnesses take the place of the DVD player's laser. This is plausible if we accept the Block Universe theory which developed from Special Relativity's non-simultaneity of events for different observers. In the Block Universe, all time coexists (the entire past, the present, and every point in the future all exist at once). Everything in the Cosmic DVD's time exists at once but we're only aware of an extremely limited number of events at any instant (these make up our present).

PROPOSAL: HUMAN AND ANIMAL INSTINCTS ARE THE RESULT OF THE UNIVERSE BEING UNIFIED BY BINARY DIGITS (AND TOPOLOGY)

If everything in the universe is ultimately composed of electronic BITS, then the universe must possess Artificial Intelligence - some prefer the term Cosmic Consciousness. Humans would occupy the highest known point on this AI ladder or spectrum of consciousness. Inanimate objects would have the lowest level of binary-digit activity, plants would have a bit more, ants

would have still more. And it increases to the human level - as well as the cosmic level, of which we're a part.

We, and every object or idea, truly are parts of the cosmos of space-time. So there certainly exists a Theory of Everything/Theory of Quantum Gravity* - but you'll never find it with bodily senses, which incorrectly tell us how separated all things are.

* Quantum Gravity is the anticipated physics theory uniting Quantum Mechanics with General Relativity, Einstein's theory of Gravity.

Finally - There's another consequence if everything in the universe is ultimately composed of electronic BITS and the cosmos is a spectrum of consciousness/artificial intelligence. It's impossible for an absence of consciousness to exist, either after death or before conception. Thus, life on Earth - not only for humans but presumably also for animals - would necessarily have to be merely a brief interlude in which we and they are apparently separated from the Universal Artificial Intelligence/Cosmic Consciousness. The knowledge called "instinct" reveals that there is no actual separation from the UAI/CC - and as we learn more about the universe, instincts will someday develop into knowledge of all things in unified space-time.

SETI, Evolution, and Time

The answer to the question "Are we alone?" might depend on two things which everyone seems to be overlooking – 1) evolution not being responsible for the origin of life, and 2) time's nonlinearity. Extraordinary events like the origin of life require extraordinary explanation. I think Carl Sagan and Charles Darwin would agree. Do you?

Evolution can be observed in the form of adaptation of structure and function to the environment but there's no reason to extrapolate this so it accounts for life's origin. In future centuries, human technology will develop terraforming and incredibly advanced genetic engineering of cells - amino acids, proteins, water, nucleic acids, etc which were gathered in space or on planets and combined. This could account for life's origin since it agrees with 19th-century chemist Louis Pasteur's proving that life can only originate from life (modern science's obsession with abiogenesis should take note of Pasteur).

There might then be no other life (on other planets) at present. When humans explore the universe, they could cause life – even technological intelligences – to emerge elsewhere. Development of time travel would allow these intelligences to exist not only in our future but also in our past ... and yes, in our present.

INFORMATION THEORY CONQUERS A RED GIANT

In about 5 billion years the Sun is supposed to expand into a red giant and engulf Mercury and Venus and possibly Earth (the expansion would probably make Earth uninhabitable in less than 1 billion years). It's entirely possible that there may not even be a red giant phase for the Sun. This relies on entropy being looked at from another angle - with the apparent randomness in quantum and cosmic processes obeying Chaos theory, in which there's a hidden order behind apparent randomness. Expansion to a Red Giant could then be described with the Information Theory vital to the Internet, mathematics, deep space, etc. In information theory, entropy is defined as a logarithmic measure of the rate of transfer of information. This definition introduces a hidden exactness, removing superficial probability. It suggests it's possible for information to be transmitted to objects, processes, or systems and restore them to a previous state - like refreshing (reloading) a computer screen. Potentially, the Sun could be prevented from becoming a red giant and returned to a previous state in a billion years (or far less) - and repeatedly every billion years - so Earth could remain habitable permanently.

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